

EVALUATING THE MICRON LEVEL PHASE DISTRIBUTION IN COMPOSITE STRUCTURES AND ITS EFFECT ON MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR USING 2D MODULUS MAPPING

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ABSTRACT

Nanoindentation was used for characterizing epoxy and epoxy/nanodiamond composites at small length scale. The effect of addition of nanodiamond (ND) to epoxy matrix was investigated at micro level through 2D modulus mapping, post and prior being subjected to loading in uniaxial direction. Variation of modulus and the evolution of their distribution with application of stress, was revealed by analysis of maps. thus giving the insight into the role of ND in controlling the mechanical behavior of the epoxy matrix. An improvement of ~ 94% in elastic modulus of epoxy was achieved with 1wt% ND. Finite element method (FEM) of the representative volume element (RVE) was used to evaluate effect of ND in stiffening epoxy matrix. There is a close agreement between predicted and experimental results. With 0.3 wt% ND the tensile strength of epoxy showed an improvement of ~ 56% along with improvement of ~66% in % strain (at break). Interfacial interaction, dispersion and strengthening mechanisms was evaluated thoroughly using transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM).

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymers matrix composites are the most evolving material due to the requirement of light weight in structural applications. FRPs are the most extensively used Polymers matrix composites in various applications which include light weight structure, automobiles, aerospace etc. The specific orientation, of macro sized fibers in these composites results into anisotropic properties. To overcome this limitation of FRPs, researchers use nano or submicron fillers, apart from the fibers, to achieve isotropic properties. In, the past few years' carbon based nanomaterials have been frequent choice as a reinforcement to PMC. The extraordinarily notable mechanical, electrical and thermal properties is what makes them the best choice[1][2][3][4]. Nanodiamond (ND) is a carbon based spherical shape nanoparticle having average size of 5–10 nm with very high surface area, high stiffness and light weight [5][6]. The spherical shape of ND offers higher surface area in comparison to shapes like sheet or tube. High mechanical properties and thermal conductivity along with rich surface chemistry makes it appropriate candidate for different applications such as biomedical [7] [8], composite [9] [10], electrochemical [11] etc. [12].

Majority of studies dedicated on addition of ND into thermoset and thermoplastic polymers has been done in recent past, especially for structural applications [10]. The studies specific to epoxy matrix [13] [14][15] [16] [17] have used ND as reinforcement both at low filler [18] and high filler content [19]. With functionalization [13] [17] [15] and without functionalization [15], for mechanical [13] [14][17] s and thermomechanical studies [15]. The improvement achieved for hardness was as high as 300 % for 7 wt% amine functionalized ND [13] while with non-functionalized ND it was ~ 47 wt% The increase in modulus of elasticity was ~470 % [19]. While for tensile strength the improvement was 150 % [20]. For fracture toughness it was ~39% for 0.1 wt % ozone treated ND [17]. However, few mentioned studies even reported agglomeration for ND loading as low as 0.1 wt%, while others went upto 7 wt% ND using functionalisation or much efficient fabrication techniques. Uniformly distribution and strong interfacial interaction with matrix, leads to this improvement. The study that used high ND content i.e. ~ 47 wt% ND used nanoindentation technique for characterizing composite [19]. Thus, ND content no more than 1 wt% is suggested for tensile and fracture studies even if functionalized, to achieve desired improvement in properties. Mechanical response of nanofiller reinforced composite depends on the dispersion of filler inside matrix, as it controls interaction between reinforcement-matrix and their accumulative reaction to loading. The probability of agglomeration is high for nanofillers, which makes its dispersion more tough. Also, mechanical response of such composite can't be explicated without gauging the dispersion of nanofillers as well as their behaviour during loading. To confirm same, both SEM, TEM analysis were done. High resolution microscopy is one of the most widely used tool to understand the dispersion and interaction of the nanofiller inside matrix. It is not a quite apt, as the size of sample used is quite small. Also, it becomes difficult, in some cases to even identify the nanofillers in polymer matrix. Therefore, they are not the most desirable to recognize the interaction between reinforcement and matrix and their behavior when loaded.

A study in literature used small angle X-ray scattering as well as TEM to explain effect of addition nanofiller on mechanical behaviour [21]. The study evaluated the mechanism behind improvement of strain along with strength in PBSA nanocomposite with 3 wt% montmorillonite. HRTEM and XRS explained that this behaviour is a result of preferential orientation of clay layers.

Apart from experimental techniques like semi analytical, analytical, as well as numerical analysis were used to foresee the response of composite by evaluating effective mechanical properties. Recently numerical analysis methods such as FEM [22] and XFEM [23][24][25] are being used to do the same. Studies using FEM to simulate heterogeneous materials with fillers having different orientation, size, shape to achieve effective properties have been reported in past [26][27]. This delivers a true all-inclusive quick reaction at low cost.

There is no study available in literature that uses modulus mapping for studying dispersion, interaction between reinforcement- matrix and their response to external load. No Numerical-analysis study is available that projects elastic modulus of ND-epoxy composite w.r.t. content. This study takes a step towards understanding the distribution of nanodiamond in epoxy and its behavior when loaded, with the help of modulus map through nanoDMA module of Triboindenter. Spatial distribution of ND in epoxy in micron level regions having higher modulus was evaluated through modulus mapping in a composite structure. The studies were carried out both without and with the application of tensile load. Investigation of maps revealed role of ND in modifying the mechanical performance of epoxy and the redistribution of the ND with load. FEM was used to investigate reinforcing effect of ND in epoxy. FEM results were compared with nanoindentation results. Tensile properties were studied for ND content from 0.1-1 wt% to find out the optimum loading condition.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

Epoxy and hardener of grade 5052 were procured from Fine Finish Organics Pvt. Ltd., Mumbai, India. NDs were purchased from Sigma Aldrich, India with purity > 97% and size of less than 10 μm .

NDs were dispersed in acetone with the help of probe sonicator, with 3 s OFF and 5 s ON and cycle for 1 hr at an amplitude of 70% along with temperature maintained at $\leq 10^\circ\text{C}$. Once, homogenized solution is achieved, epoxy is added to the solution part by part followed by mixing in between. To ensure good dispersion of ND in epoxy the solution was sonicated for 15 min in between each portion of epoxy, after all the epoxy is added to solution it is sonicated for another 20 min. This solution is finally placed above magnetic stirrer for 5-6 hours at 70°C , rotating at an rpm of 400, to evaporate the complete acetone. Once acetone is removed completely, hardener is added to epoxy in ratio 100:38 (epoxy : hardener) parts by weight. Finally, it is kept in vacuum in order to eliminate any air trapped inside. The mixture is then discharged into silicon molds made out and left for curing at room temperature.

The ND concentration chosen for this study was 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5 & 1 wt%. The content of reinforcement was taken low intentionally to elude agglomeration.

3 CHARACTERIZATION

Tensile test was done according to ASTM D638 (V) using H25K-S UTM (Tinius Olsen Testing Machine Company, USA). UTS and strain (%) are the two properties obtained from tensile test. Hysitron TI-950 Triboindenter was used for performing Nano indentation test. The triboindenter fitted with a 3 sided berkovich indenter having tip radius of ~ 100 nm and loading rate of $100 \mu\text{N/s}$ with highest load of $500 \mu\text{N}$ with 2 s holding time at peak load was used to find modulus of elasticity and hardness of the composite. 15 indents per sample were taken to evaluate elastic modulus. NanoDMA mode was used to obtain the modulus maps of polished samples. SPM assimilated to nanoindenter was used to scan surface during mapping. NanoDMA was done at $2 \mu\text{N}$ static load and $0.3 \mu\text{N}$ dynamic load with 200 Hz frequency.

Numerical analysis of RVE was done using ABAQUS software was used to evaluate elastic modulus of ND particles in epoxy. Periodic boundary conditions were used to evaluate elastic properties in this study as uniform displacement boundary condition overestimates the properties, while uniform traction boundary condition underestimates the same.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Modulus of elasticity of ND reinforced epoxy composite was measured through nanoindentation. Elastic modulus was seen to increase with ND concentration (Fig. 1). The highest improvement of ~94%. Strong interface between the ND and epoxy resists deformation and thus lead to effective load sharing between two. Modulus of epoxy didn't improve as significantly with 0.5 wt% ND as with 1 wt% ND although the reinforcement content was doubled. Irregularities generated due to agglomeration of ND lead to poor interfacial bonding. However, hardness is comparatively less sensitive to agglomeration. Thus, agglomeration tend to affects both elastic modulus and hardness but to different degree. As strong interaction between ND and epoxy is the main reason behind improved modulus of elasticity so even a small abnormality is quite severe.

Figure 1. Elastic modulus for ND reinforced epoxy composite

Representative stress strain curve for epoxy as well as ND reinforced epoxy is shown in Fig. 2. UTS and % strain were calculated from the stress-strain curve. Five samples per composition were tested for repeatability, average of which was reported along with error bars. The highest improvement in UTS was ~56% with 0.3 wt% ND over neat epoxy. Dominant strengthening mechanism is efficient load transfer which is achieved due to good dispersion of ND in epoxy leading to strong interface between the two. With increase in ND above 0.3wt% UTS decreased. Although the UTS and % strain was higher for all composites than pure epoxy. High surface energy of ND, results in agglomeration thereby decreasing the tensile strength. Any irregularities are the weakest point to efficient load transfer leading to failure of composite well below its capability when loaded. This proves how susceptible is the composite to failure.

Figure 2. Stress vs strain plot for ND reinforced epoxy composite

Mechanical studies proved the potential of ND addition to epoxy. It did not give a proper picture of interface and its behaviour during load sharing. 2D modulus mapping was done on all three

planes of the epoxy as well as ND reinforced epoxy composite prior and after post being loaded by tensile load (Fig. 3(a)).

Figure. 3(a) Schematic of tensile sample used for nanoDMA and **(b)** Modulus maps for epoxy as well as ND-epoxy before being subjected to tensile loading

The modulus map for epoxy as well as ND reinforced epoxy composite prior to tensile loading are shown in Fig. 3(b). Storage modulus suggests stiffness, which have a tendency to improve with the addition of ND. However, storage modulus and elastic modulus are different properties therefore they have different value but same trend. With the addition of ND the average storage modulus value attained for the same area increased three times from ~5 GPa to ~15 GPa with 1 wt% ND. The NDs were seen uniformly distributed within matrix, with ND rich regions ~ 550 nm. These ND rich regions are present uniformly throughout the matrix. On magnifying further into the ND rich regions (Fig. 6(b)) it can be seen that they are not agglomerations, that would lead to stress concentration. While departing out from the centre of these red regions (ND rich regions) the stress field i.e. the region upto which the effect of load sharing by ND can be evidenced as yellow and green regions. The stress field reduces as we move away from the centre of these ND rich regions leading to lower modulus. Also the area under the stress field is not just pure epoxy but contains ND as well, although, not as much as in those red domains.

The modulus map for epoxy and ND-epoxy composite prior to tensile loading are shown in Fig. 4(a & b). As seen from Fig. 4(b) the nanodiamonds were dispersed all along matrix quite uniformly having strong interface with epoxy. This eventually lead to efficient load sharing which increases the overall modulus of the matrix. The regions of high modulus are ND rich regions having efficient load sharing by NDs. Even the areas around these domains have higher modulus then rest of the matrix which signifies the stress field around the ND up to which the effect of load sharing can be experienced. After being subjected to uniaxial tensile loading. For ND reinforced epoxy composite (Fig. 4c) it can be clearly seen from the figures that the applied stress not only aligns the NDs in the stress direction but improves dispersion by redistributing the ND thus reducing the domain size leading to improved strength as well as ductility.

Figure 4. Modulus maps organized in 3D before tensile loading (a) epoxy and (b) ND reinforced epoxy, and after tensile loading (c) ND reinforced epoxy

In order to evaluate the effective elastic properties of the composite the principle of strain energy equivalence was applied.

Principle of strain energy equivalence was implemented in ABAQUS software using Python script to evaluate the effective elastic properties of the composite.

In this method, the strain energy of the heterogeneous composite is compared with the strain energy of the equivalent homogeneous material under similar loading and boundary conditions. The total strain energy of a body is given by

$$\bar{U} = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \sigma_{ij} \varepsilon_{ij} dV \quad (1)$$

To evaluate the Elastic modulus (E), a uniaxial tensile strain was applied in the x-direction, then the strain energy of homogenous medium is given as,

$$U_{xx} = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \sigma_{xx} \varepsilon_{xx} dV \quad (2)$$

By equating the strain energy of the equivalent homogenous medium with the strain energy heterogeneous composite, the elastic modulus is obtained using the following expression

$$\bar{U} = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \sigma_{xx} \varepsilon_{xx} dV \quad (3)$$

Where, $\sigma_{xx} = E\varepsilon_{xx}$, σ_{xx} and ε_{xx} are the stress and strain components respectively. \bar{U} is the numerically calculated strain energy of heterogeneous medium, due to the action of uniaxial tensile strain. The effective modulus, obtained from numerical analysis, is compared to that experimentally measured using instrumented indentation as shown in Fig. 5, which were a close match.

Figure 5. Comparative variation of the effective elastic modulus with weight fraction of the ND obtained from the numerical and experimental analysis

5 CONCLUSIONS

2D-modulus mapping proved to be a great tool exhaustive investigation of the part played by ND in changing the mechanical behavior of composites. Investigation of maps gave a clear picture of distribution of ND in epoxy, with regard to 3-D dispersion of ND rich regions at micron level in composite. ND shared the load of epoxy thus providing high opposition to epoxy against distortion increasing modulus of elasticity by ~94%. Modulus of elasticity values generated from simulation are very similar to that attained through nanoindentation. Incorporating ND to epoxy increased the UTS and % strain of epoxy matrix. The tensile properties showed highest improvement with 0.3 wt% ND loading. Increasing ND content further, reduced the properties as a result of agglomeration. For all compositions of ND reinforced epoxy composite the properties were higher than for only epoxy. The agglomeration was high enough at 1 wt% ND. Improved strength was achieved as a result of strong interface which lead to better load distribution.

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